

From Self-Realization to Social Harmony: The Living Spirit of Idealistic Education

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Abstract: *Idealistic philosophy recognizes the soul, consciousness, and spiritual reality as the fundamental basis of human life. According to this view, the chief aim of education is self-realization and the development of the individual's inner potential. Education is not merely the acquisition of knowledge; rather, it is a harmonious process of intellectual, moral, spiritual, and physical development. The eternal values of Truth, Goodness, and Beauty form the core objectives of education in Idealism. Idealists emphasize the inclusion of religion, ethics, literature, and fine arts in the curriculum to cultivate these higher values. The teacher plays a vital role as a moral exemplar and spiritual guide, inspiring students through character and conduct. The school is regarded as a sacred place for spiritual growth, and self-discipline is encouraged over external control. Overall, Idealism views education as a powerful means for the complete development of personality and the creation of an ideal society.*

Keywords: *Idealism, Self-Realization, Truth, Goodness and Beauty, Moral and Spiritual Development, Holistic Education*

INTRODUCTION: Throughout different ages, various philosophical doctrines have influenced educational thought. Among them, Idealism is considered one of the most ancient and influential philosophies. The philosophy that gives primary importance to the soul, mind, or the world of ideas and emphasizes spiritual realization as the ultimate goal of life is known as Idealism. According to idealists, the entire universe is the manifestation of a single, all-pervading spiritual reality. They believe that the visible material world is not the ultimate truth; rather, it is only a temporary or illusory reflection. The real truth lies in an unseen spiritual realm, which is governed by an omnipotent God or the Supreme Being. The human mind or soul is regarded as a part of that Supreme Reality. From this perspective, the chief aim of human life is self-realization — the realization of the true nature of the Supreme Being through inner awareness. When a person attains this realization, the ideals of Truth, Goodness, and Beauty are manifested in their life, and these values are reflected in their character and conduct.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY: The major objectives of this study are:

1. To analyze the fundamental principles of Idealistic philosophy.
2. To identify the aims of education according to Idealism.
3. To evaluate the relevance of Idealism in the contemporary educational system.
4. To critically examine the strengths and limitations of Idealistic educational thought.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY: The discussion cum descriptive method was adopted for the present study. Data have been collected from various documents, such as writings, essay and letters, which serve as primary sources. Important books, journals, and web pages have been used as secondary sources. Content analysis has been carried out, and all relevant reports and dispatches have been considered as primary sources. This work is qualitative in nature.

DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY: This study is entirely based on philosophical analysis. It does not include empirical data or field-based investigation.

THE PRINCIPLE OF IDEALISM: Idealist philosophers fundamentally believe in a spiritual reality. According to them, consciousness, soul, and ideas constitute the ultimate truth. The main principles of Idealism may be presented as follows:

1. Idealism gives highest importance to the soul or the world of ideas. It holds that the true nature of human beings is spiritual; therefore, spiritual life and inner realization are given special significance. For this reason, Idealism is regarded as a spiritualistic philosophy.
2. The ultimate aim of Idealism is liberation or salvation (Moksha). The supreme goal of human life is spiritual development and the realization of the Absolute Truth.
3. Idealists believe that the entire universe is the manifestation of one unified spiritual reality. From this standpoint, the spiritual world alone is the ultimate truth, while the material or physical world is temporary and illusory.
4. Idealism is theistic in nature. It acknowledges the existence of God or the Supreme Being. Idealists maintain that behind the visible world lies an eternal spiritual realm governed by an omnipotent God. Human beings are considered parts of that Supreme Reality. Therefore, the realization of the Supreme Being through self-realization is regarded as the true purpose of human life. Hence, Idealism is known as a philosophy of self-realization.
5. A fundamental principle of Idealism is the immortality of the soul. Though the body is mortal, the soul is eternal and indestructible. The imperishable nature of the soul is considered a central truth in Idealist philosophy.
6. According to Idealism, values are not externally acquired; they are inherent and eternal within human nature. Values are internal and unchangeable in character. When a person realizes the true nature of the Supreme Being through self-realization, Truth, Goodness, and Beauty manifest in their life—this marks the awakening of true values.
7. Another important principle of Idealism is that it denies the ultimate reality of the material world and advances with the world of ideas or consciousness at its center. Spirituality forms the fundamental basis and guiding force of this philosophy.

AIMS OF EDUCATION ACCORDING TO IDEALISTIC PHILOSOPHY: In Idealistic philosophy, education is not merely the acquisition of knowledge; it is a sacred process for the holistic development of human personality. The aims of education, according to Idealism, are profound and multidimensional. They may be presented as follows:

1. Self-Realization: The foremost aim of education, according to Idealist philosophers, is self-realization. Education helps in unfolding the innate powers and hidden potentialities within the individual. Swami Vivekananda stated, “*Education is the manifestation of perfection already in man.*” This means that education

brings out the inherent perfection within a person. Therefore, the ultimate aim of education is inward development and realization of the true self.

2. Intellectual Development: Idealistic education gives great importance to intellectual growth. Through education, the learner's reasoning power, thinking ability, and creative faculties are developed to the highest extent. This enables the individual to adjust harmoniously with the environment and make wise decisions.

3. Spiritual Development: According to Idealism, the true nature of human beings is spiritual. Hence, one of the chief aims of education is the awakening of spiritual consciousness. Through spiritual development, a person strives to realize the unity of the individual soul with the Supreme Reality. In this lies the fulfillment of Idealistic thought.

4. Development of Moral Values: Education, in the Idealistic view, aims at the cultivation of moral character. The development of moral values enables students to distinguish between right and wrong, truth and falsehood, and good and evil. Thus, education helps in building an ethical and virtuous life.

5. Physical Development: Idealism also recognizes the importance of physical development. A sound body is considered the foundation of a sound mind. Therefore, education should also promote physical well-being alongside mental and spiritual growth.

6. Universal Education: Idealists believe that education should be universal in nature. It must be accessible to all, irrespective of caste, creed, religion, gender, or economic status. The spread of education helps individuals realize that all human beings are manifestations of the same Supreme Reality.

7. Development of Personality: Another important aim of Idealistic education is the full development of personality. When an individual's inner qualities are properly nurtured, their true self finds complete expression, enabling them to contribute creatively to society.

8. Formation of a Pure Life: Idealistic philosophy holds that education should create an ideal environment for cultivating a pure and noble life. Through such a life, spiritual growth and self-realization become possible.

Thus, in Idealism, education is regarded as a powerful means for achieving intellectual excellence, moral refinement, spiritual awakening, and the complete development of human personality.

CURRICULUM ACCORDING TO IDEALISM: In harmony with the aims of education, the views expressed by Idealists regarding the curriculum also reveal originality and depth. According to them, the curriculum should be designed in such a way that it promotes the full development of the inner self of the learner.

Idealists lay special emphasis on three eternal values—Truth, Goodness (or Righteousness), and Beauty. These three ideals guide and regulate the different spheres of human activity. They are reflected in the intellectual, moral, physical, and aesthetic dimensions of human life.

Furthermore, Idealists believe that three fundamental needs operate at the core of human vitality: the need for knowledge, the need for devotion, and the need for activity. The need for knowledge fosters intellectual growth; the need for devotion awakens moral and spiritual consciousness; and the need for activity inspires purposeful action and creativity.

In this context, Idealists maintain that the curriculum should include subjects that contribute to the holistic development of human personality. Therefore, reli-

gion, ethics, fine arts, and the humanities should form essential components of the curriculum. Through such a curriculum, the eternal ideals of Truth, Goodness, and Beauty can be effectively cultivated in human life.

Ross has proposed a well-structured framework of curriculum for the all-round development of a student's personality. According to them, education should ensure the harmonious growth of both body and soul.

1)Physical Activities: For the complete development of the learner's individuality, physical activities should form an essential part of the curriculum. To promote physical fitness and efficiency, activities such as games, physical exercise, gymnastics, and similar forms of training are to be included. In addition, health science should also be incorporated into the curriculum to ensure sound physical and mental well-being.

2)Spiritual Activities: Idealists maintain that along with physical development, spiritual growth is equally essential in education. Therefore, the curriculum should include subjects that nurture the inner consciousness of the learner. For this purpose, subjects such as literature, language, history, science, mathematics, geography, ethics, fine arts, music, drawing, poetry, and religious studies are regarded as integral components of spiritual activities.

Thus, the Idealistic curriculum aims at the integrated development of body and soul, ultimately leading to the formation of a well-balanced and fully developed personality.

TEACHING METHOD: According to Idealists, education is the natural and spontaneous development of the child's inner self. Therefore, the method of teaching should be in harmony with the child's interests, tendencies, and surrounding environment. With this objective, different philosophers have suggested different methods of teaching, such as the question-answer method of Socrates, the discourse method of Plato, the inductive and deductive methods of Aristotle, the observation method of Johann Heinrich Pestalozzi, the play-way method of Friedrich Froebel, and the instruction method of Johann Friedrich Herbart.

From the Idealistic point of view, the classroom is not merely a place for delivering lessons; it is a sacred space for spiritual learning. Here, the mind of the learner develops spontaneously and opportunities for self-learning are created. From such an environment emerge knowledge, skills, and character development.

Therefore, Idealist philosophers have emphasized several teaching methods and techniques, including the lecture method, explanation method, discussion method, question-answer method, play-way method, heuristic or discovery method, observation method, and practical or activity-based method.

Thus, the Idealistic method of teaching aims at developing the learner's inner potential and guiding them toward intellectual excellence, moral refinement, and spiritual enrichment.

TEACHER: According to Idealism, a teacher is not merely a transmitter of knowledge, but a person of noble character and high ideals. The teacher should lead a morally elevated and spiritually devoted life, serving as a living influence in the inner life of the students.

In short, the teacher must stand before students as an example of a great and ideal life. He or she should be a spiritual guide, a loving guardian, and a constant source of inspiration. The teacher's conduct, values, and personality should be so exemplary that students feel naturally motivated to follow and emulate those virtues.

Thus, in Idealistic philosophy, the teacher is regarded as a living model whose character and life play a vital role in shaping the moral, spiritual, and personal development of the learners.

In this context, Giovanni Gentile said, "*Teacher is a spiritual symbol of right conduct.*" A teacher influences students through his philosophy of life and the qualities of his personality.

According to Idealistic philosophy, the teacher should be a helper and a guide to the learner. Therefore, Sri Aurobindo stated, "*The teacher is not an instructor or task-master; he is a helper and guide.*" This means that a teacher is not merely someone who gives instructions, but one who supports and guides students in their growth.

Thus, the truly worthy teacher is one who has attained complete self-realization, for only such a person can genuinely guide students toward the realization of their own higher selves.

CONCEPT OF SCHOOL IN IDEALISM: In Idealistic philosophy, the concept of the school possesses a distinctive and profound significance. Idealists believe that the entire universe is united through a universal spiritual reality. In order to realize this unity, the school environment must reflect and embody that spiritual harmony. The school should be shaped as a sacred place where students, through the process of education, gradually come to realize their own inner spiritual self.

DISCIPLINE: The Idealist philosophers' concept of discipline is closely related to their principle of spontaneous activity. According to them, self-discipline is absolutely essential for self-realization. A disordered and restless mind cannot achieve true self-realization.

However, such discipline cannot be imposed from outside through strict rules and external restrictions. Imposed control tends to suppress the developing self or ego and does not lead the individual toward genuine self-realization. External compulsion may create obedience, but it cannot nurture inner growth.

Therefore, Idealist philosophers argue that discipline in education should be internal and spontaneous. It should arise from within the learner rather than being forced upon them. There should be no unnecessary restriction on the student's thinking, activity, or natural interests. Freedom must be maintained in all aspects of the educational process.

This type of discipline, based on free and active participation, is known as "free discipline" in Idealist educational philosophy. (Roy, 2020)

Thomas and Lang observed, "*Freedom is the cry of Naturalists while discipline is that of Idealists.*" (Ghorai, 2024)

THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF IDEALISM IN THE FIELD OF PRESENT EDUCATION :

1. Idealism places great emphasis on the mental and spiritual development of the individual. Therefore, the primary aim of education, according to Idealist philosophy, is the full development of the inner self or inherent potential of a person. Education is not merely the acquisition of information; rather, it is a process of self-realization and spiritual upliftment.
2. Idealist philosophers give special importance to self-realization. They believe that true knowledge is closely connected with the spiritual world and is achieved through inner awakening rather than through mere sensory experience. Thus, education should help individuals realize their true nature.

3. Idealism also stresses simple living and high thinking. It gives importance to moral and religious education for the character development of children. Three eternal values—Truth, Goodness, and Beauty—are considered the foundation of moral life and education.
4. For the formation of an ideal society and the complete development of personality, Idealism supports universal education. The purpose of education is to cultivate moral values and promote harmony in society.
5. Idealism advocates self-discipline or free discipline, allowing students to learn in an atmosphere of inner control rather than external force. It emphasizes internal motivation over strict external authority.
6. Finally, in Idealist philosophy, the teacher holds a very significant position. The teacher is not only an instructor but also a guide and role model. Students shape their ideals and character by following the example set by the teacher. At the same time, attention is given to the interests, abilities, and environment of the learner in the educational process (Ghorai,2024).

CRITICISM OF IDEALISM: Although Idealism has made significant contributions to education, it also has certain limitations. These may be explained in a different way as follows:

1. Idealism gives excessive importance to the mental and spiritual aspects of human life. As a result, physical development and social realities are comparatively neglected. This one-sided emphasis may hinder the balanced and all-round development of an individual.
2. The philosophy stresses the attainment of eternal values such as Truth, Goodness, and Beauty. However, critics argue that values may change according to time, society, and culture. Therefore, considering them as completely permanent and unchangeable may not always be realistic.
3. Idealistic education places greater emphasis on humanities, moral, and religious subjects, while science, technology, and practical knowledge receive comparatively less importance. In the modern age, where scientific thinking and technical skills are essential, this approach may appear limited.
4. In this system, the teacher is given a higher position than the learner. The teacher is seen as an authority and role model, which may sometimes reduce the active participation and independence of students.
5. Idealism does not give much importance to activity-centered or experience-based curricula. Practical work and learning by doing are not strongly emphasized.
6. Finally, Idealism prioritizes spiritual knowledge over material or worldly knowledge. As a result, practical skills necessary for everyday life may not receive adequate attention.

ROLE OF IDEALISTIC EDUCATION IN ESTABLISHING PEACE AND DISCIPLINE IN THE PRESENT AGE: Idealistic education is not confined merely to the field of formal schooling; it also holds profound relevance in establishing peace, discipline, and moral harmony in contemporary society. In the modern world, where violence, intolerance, materialism, and excessive competition are increasingly disturbing social balance, Idealistic philosophy offers a deeper spiritual perspective for restoring inner and social harmony.

According to Idealism, every human being possesses an inner spiritual self, which is a part of the Supreme Consciousness. When an individual realizes this inner self through the process of self-realization, a union occurs between the indi-

vidual soul and the Supreme Reality. This spiritual awakening leads to the development of higher consciousness. As a result, inner peace, self-control, and moral discipline naturally emerge within the individual.

Through such spiritual development, a person gradually builds an ideal and well-regulated life. Discipline, in this sense, is not externally imposed but internally cultivated. A spiritually awakened individual becomes calm, balanced, and ethically responsible. Thus, peace and order are established first within the individual and then reflected in society.

Idealistic thought encourages individuals to rise above selfish interests and recognize the spiritual unity of all humanity. When a person truly realizes their inner self, they understand that all human beings are connected through a universal spiritual bond. This realization inspires people to pursue peace, moral values, and ethical conduct. Education, therefore, becomes not merely a means of career advancement, but a process of cultivating humanity, character, and universal brotherhood.

Consequently, social evils such as hatred, violence, jealousy, and conflict gradually diminish. In their place, mutual respect, tolerance, compassion, and unity develop among individuals. From this perspective, Idealistic education provides a strong philosophical foundation for the establishment of world peace and social harmony.

Among modern thinkers, Swami Vivekananda and Sri Aurobindo attached great importance to Idealistic philosophical thought. Swami Vivekananda viewed education as the manifestation of the perfection already inherent in man and emphasized the unity of humanity. Sri Aurobindo stressed the spiritual evolution of human consciousness and regarded education as a means for the integral transformation of human life.

Therefore, it may be concluded that Idealistic educational philosophy remains highly relevant in the present age. It not only promotes intellectual and moral development but also serves as a powerful instrument for establishing peace, discipline, unity, and spiritual harmony in human society.

CONCLUSION: From the above discussion, it can be concluded that Idealistic philosophy regards education not merely as a process of acquiring knowledge, but as a sacred means for the complete development of human life. It upholds the supremacy of the soul and consciousness and considers self-realization as the ultimate goal of life. Therefore, the primary aim of education is the unfolding of the individual's inner potential, the formation of moral character, and the awakening of spiritual consciousness.

Idealism emphasizes the cultivation of the eternal values of Truth, Goodness, and Beauty for the creation of an ideal individual and an ideal society. In matters of curriculum, teaching methods, teacher–student relationship, and school environment, special importance is given to morality and spirituality. The teacher is viewed as a living model of noble ideals, while the learner is seen as a developing spiritual being.

Thus, Idealistic philosophy establishes education as a powerful instrument for character formation, spiritual upliftment, and the harmonious development of personality, and its influence continues to shape educational thought even today.

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